

A COMPOSITE HYDROGEL FOR THE REPLACEMENT OF THE *NUCLEUS PULPOSUS*

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SUMMARY

A polymer material system has been developed to propose an injectable, UV and *in situ* curable hydrogel with properties similar to the native *nucleus pulposus* of intervertebral discs. The synthesis of a novel hydrogel polymer based on Tween 20 molecules was realised first, then its polymerisation kinetics was determined for different concentrations of crosslinker. The compression behaviours of dry and hydrated polymers were compared. Excellent swelling properties were achieved by tuning the chemistry of the novel hydrogel which is currently reinforced to extend the range of mechanical properties.

Keywords: composite hydrogel, UV curing, polymer, nucleus pulposus, injectable

INTRODUCTION

Back pain due to the degeneration of the *nucleus pulposus* (NP), that is the hydrogel core of the intervertebral disc, is currently a major public health issue. Hydrogels have been developed over the last 40 years for their hydrophilic character and potential biocompatibility [1] in response to the rapid evolution of the field of tissue engineering. Tissue repair or implantation initially made use of natural substitutes but the limited supply of healthy organs and tissues has led to a need for synthetic replacements [1]. Hydrogels are indeed close in properties to many living tissues. It is therefore logical to consider hydrogels as candidates for the material repair of damaged discs. Several types of hydrogels are used for NP replacement but none has gained universal acceptance. The available implants can be divided in two categories: desiccated preformed hydrogels and injectable *in situ* curing hydrogels. There are still many issues with hydrogels for this kind of implant, but the most important is the mechanical weakness of the current material. Composite hydrogels are being developed by Xiang et al. [2] and Haragushi et al. [3], who have demonstrated the feasibility of the concept. However, their development has not yet included complete mechanical and kinetic studies and optimization of the composite gel for a given application. The goal of this study is to develop a composite hydrogel which is biocompatible, injectable and can be cured *in situ*. UV curable polymers are already widely used in dentistry and the great advantages of this crosslinking method are the absence of potentially toxic crosslinkers and the short time of reaction in a solvent-free environment. To fulfil these requirements, novel polymer molecules based on Tween 20 have been synthesized. Methacrylate polymers

are typically formed by free radical chain polymerization. One of the major drawbacks of this mechanism is the inhibition of the chain formation by molecular oxygen. A great deal of research has been done to overcome this issue by cost-effective means which include the removal of oxygen from the reacting environment [4] or the adjunction of molecules that reduce the impact of molecular oxygen [5, 6]. Already in 1977, N-vinyl-2-pyrrolidone (NVP) was reported to significantly decrease the inhibition of acrylate polymerization by oxygen [7]. White et al. [8] showed that NVP enhanced the polymerization rate. Therefore, and due to the fact that the final application of this hydrogel cannot be carried out in a nitrogen atmosphere, the synthesis and polymerisation of Tween 20 methacrylates and NVP were investigated to obtain novel hydrogels.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Synthesis of Tween 20 methacrylates

Tween 20 mono-(T1), di-(T2) or tri-(T3)methacrylate were synthesized by coupling of methacryloyl chloride to Tween 20 (surfactant from Sigma Aldrich) in the presence of 4-(*N,N*-dimethylamino)pyridine (Sigma Aldrich) using tetrahydrofuran (THF, Acros Organics) as solvent. The product was then filtered and passed through a chromatographic column containing silica gel 60 (Acros Organics) and the selected fraction was rotor evaporated to separate the solvent. The monomers were characterized by FTIR (Perkin-Elmer Spectrum One spectrometer, Spectrum Spotlight 300). For each sample, 64 scans were recorded between 4000 cm^{-1} and 400 cm^{-1} with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . The mechanism of reaction is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Synthesis of Tween 20 methacrylates

Preparation of samples

The samples were composed of T3 as crosslinker, N-vinyl-2-pyrrolidone (NVP), water and initiator Irgacure 2959 (I2959, Ciba). NVP was used as purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Switzerland and I2959 was used as an aqueous solution (0.05 wt% in water). The volume of initiator and water in these tests remained constant at 10 vol% and 40 vol% respectively and the concentrations of T3 and NVP changed.

Evolution of kinetics by photorheology

The evolution of the network was followed by photorheology on a controlled strain dynamic rotational rheometer (ARES, Rheometrics Scientific), coupled with a UV light source. The solutions were tested between 2 parallel plates of 25mm in diameter. The upper plate was a quartz plate through which the UV light could reach the sample. A sample of 200 μ l was loaded on the lower plate and the gap was set to 0.3mm. A scanning of strain and frequency was made before crosslinking to determine the conditions of the tests. It was observed that at 15% of strain and with a frequency of 10Hz at room temperature the material was in its linear viscoelastic range. The evolution of viscosity ν was measured for 30 minutes for samples with a T3 concentration of 1 vol%, 4.5 vol%, 8 vol%, 11.5 vol% and 15 vol%. Duplicate experiments showed excellent reproducibility. The UV source used for photorheology was an EXFO Omnicure S2000. The UV intensity used was 15 mW/cm² and was measured using the Sola-Check (Solatell, UK). The UV intensity varied by less than 10% between two illuminations.

Mechanical performance of hydrogels

A well mixed solution of T3, NVP, I2959 and water was used to cast samples of 2 cm in diameter and 5 mm high in silicon moulds resistant to UV light. Samples were exposed for 30 min to UV light with an intensity of 140 mW/cm² measured between 270 and 370nm (SolaCheck, Solatell, UK). The samples were then redimensioned with a punch to cylinders of 8 mm of diameter and 5 mm high and tested in compression directly after polymerization, after drying at 100°C for 24h and after 24h of rehydration in phosphate buffered saline (PBS) at 37°C. Two concentrations of T3 were tested: 8 vol% (T3-8) and 15 vol% (T3-15). The stiffness of the hydrogel was determined in compression with DMA measurements. The samples were loaded between two parallel plates of 1 cm in diameter, enclosed in a furnace for isothermal measurements. The measuring device was a dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA Q800, TA Instruments). The downer plate was fixed and the upper plate compressed the samples. A force ramp of 3N/min was applied until the force reached a maximum of 15N. For the rehydrated samples, the compression tests were made in immersion mode, in a PBS solution. The elasticity modulus E was calculated from the stress-strain curves between 0 and 10% of strain because the compressive strain of a healthy *nucleus pulposus* ranges from -10% to 10% [9]. All tests were duplicated, showing a good reproducibility.

Swelling behaviour

The swelling behaviour of the hydrogel samples with concentrations of T3 of 8 vol% and 15 vol% was followed gravimetrically by measuring the weight gain with the time of immersion in PBS at room temperature. Every 15 minutes, the samples were weighed after drying the surface. The measurements were taken until equilibrium was reached. During the swelling process a considerable increase of the dimensions of the original samples was observed. All measurements were triplicated to insure reproducibility. The swelling ratio was calculated as follows:

$$SR = W_s / W_d = (W_w - W_d) / W_d \quad (1)$$

Where W_s is the weight of PBS in the swollen hydrogel after the equilibrium has been reached at room temperature, W_w is the weight of the wet sample and W_d is the weight of the hydrogel at time 0.

Biocompatibility of hydrogels

Cylinders of hydrogel (1 cm diameter and 5 mm height) kept in PBS were sterilized in an autoclave and then placed in Petri dishes. Foetal cells of cartilage were distributed around the samples, without touching the gels. Cell viability under static cultures was measured at day 7.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tween 20 mono-, di- and tri-methacrylates of high purity and relatively low polydispersity were obtained after the synthesis. The general synthetic route for coupling a vinyl moiety with a hydroxylated polymer was first described by Hennink [10] and the grafting of dextran with glycidyl methacrylate [11, 12]. The Tween 20 hydroxyl endgroups react with the methacryl moieties of the chloride in the presence of a base (DMAP), which acts as a catalyst, to form the Tween methacrylates. Under the basic reaction conditions, the hydroxyl groups of Tween 20 are polarized and react subsequently with the less hindered methylene carbon of the epoxy group of MeOCl, according to Figure 1. The diminution of hydroxyl groups was demonstrated qualitatively by FTIR. Methacryloyl chloride is very reactive and the formed byproduct was a triethylamine/HCl salt [13], which was very difficult to remove. Given sufficient reaction time, only a slight excess of methacryloyl chloride was necessary to achieve good conversion. Purification can therefore be an issue due to the byproduct and the unreacted material. Column chromatography was the method of choice for this purification and the yields were around 80%.

Qualitative analysis of the degree of substitution of the hydroxyl groups was performed by FTIR.

Figure 2: FTIR spectra of Tween 20 and derived monomers. The signals correspond to: 3500(ν_{O-H}), 2900 (ν_{C-H}), 1700 ($\nu_{C=O}$), 1100 ($\nu_{C-O, ester}$), 800 ($\nu_{C-H, C=CH_2}$).

The aim was to demonstrate the decrease of the hydroxyl groups from the initial molecule of Tween 20 but also the increase of the methacrylate groups or more exactly of the carbonyl groups (C=O). In Figure 2, the FTIR spectra of all monomers and the initial molecule are displayed. The absorption of the -OH group is at around 3500 cm^{-1} and the absorption of the C=O group is at 1725 cm^{-1} . The first information that can be deduced from the spectra is that a pure monomer solution is obtained after column chromatography. As we superpose the spectra, they are identical, except for the new groups on the molecule. Therefore, the structure of the backbone of the monomers is the same as the Tween 20 backbone structure. In our spectra, we can see a significant decrease of the -OH group absorption (arrow). The signal decreases as the amount of methacrylate groups in the molecule increases and for the Tween 20 3-MA, the signal disappears. Regarding the absorption of the C=O groups, a change is also observed. The signal increases as the methacrylate groups increase. However, this signal is difficult to analyze because the peaks superpose. This is due to other C=O groups present in the backbone of the molecule.

Due to its tri-branched structure and high reactivity, T3 was used as crosslinker in the hydrogel formulation in order to obtain a 3-D network. Photorheology gives an overview of the copolymerization kinetics by following the evolution of the viscosity. The time at which the viscosity reaches the plateau as shown in Figure 3, allows an estimate of the time needed for the crosslinking to complete. The concentration of T3 has an influence on the time needed for the copolymerization.

Figure 3: Viscosity of hydrogels measured as a function of irradiation time for different T3 concentrations at room temperature and at 15 mW/cm^2 (15% of strain, 10 Hz).

Figure 3 shows that at very small concentrations of T3, the plateau is not reached, which means that the polymerization is not complete. A small concentration of T3 means less reactive species in the solution. Increasing the T3 concentration also increases the polymerization rate. At a concentration of 4.5% and 8% in volume of T3, the time needed for polymerization is around 400 s whereas with concentrations of 11.5%vol and 15%vol the time of polymerization is around 700 s. A fast polymerization is a key requirement for this application. The reason of this difference is explained by the step mechanisms of free radical crosslinking. After the initiation, the chain growth starts

with the radicals attacking other molecules and forming the network. Once the network is formed, the mobility of the still free molecules is decreased and the crosslinking becomes diffusion-controlled. The last molecules have difficulties in moving in the network and in combining with other molecules and the rate of reaction decreases dramatically. The value of viscosity when the plateau is reached varies with the T3 concentration. One order of magnitude is the highest difference and between the two highest T3 concentrations, the value is almost the same. With large concentrations of T3, the crosslinking density will increase and that explains the increase in viscosity. From these results, it was chosen to work with concentrations above 8 vol% because the difference in the time of copolymerization is not significant for this application. It is however important to have hydrogels that can bear a certain amount of load in compression and therefore, hydrogels with higher amount of T3 will be stiffer according to the evolution of viscosity. Figure 4 shows the mechanical behaviour of two hydrogels with two different concentrations of T3.

Figure 4: Stress-strain curves of developed hydrogels with two different concentrations of crosslinker T3 and at different test conditions.

Increasing the T3 concentration also increases the stiffness of the samples as predicted by the photorheology results. This is due to an increased number of bonds formed during the polymerization and thus leading to a higher crosslinking density. The presence of water in the network also determines the mechanical behaviour of the sample. For dried samples, when no water is present, there is a linear relationship between strain and stress; however, once water is part of the network, this relation is no more linear. As the applied stress increases, the samples become stiffer as if the network undergoes a reorganization of the polymer chains. The water facilitates the movements of the polymer chains and this explains the non-linear behaviour of the samples. The small barrelling effect of the hydrogel cylinders when compressed could also contribute to the non-linear behaviour of the curves. The moduli of elasticity E of the samples were calculated from the slope of the stress-strain curves between 0% and 10% of strain. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Elasticity modulus E of hydrogels with two different concentrations of T3.

	E (dried samples) [MPa]	E (after polymerization) [MPa]	E (after rehydration) [MPa]
T3-8	2.2	0.05	0.03
T3-15	2.5	0.08	0.04

As expected, as the amount of water in the network decreases, the moduli increase, indicating a stiffening of the network. The mechanism of swelling for a hydrogel implies a loosening of the polymer chains as the water enters the network. Therefore, the mechanical properties of the hydrated samples are influenced by the swelling behaviour of the hydrogel. From literature [14, 15], the value of E for the native *nucleus pulposus* is in the range of 1.5 MPa to 3 MPa. Here, the modulus for the hydrated samples, which are the ones used for the application, are still two orders of magnitude below the desired value and the changing of the chemistry does not improve dramatically the stiffness of the structure.

Figure 5 shows the variation of the mass of samples as a function of the swelling time for hydrogels with composition indicated. The equilibrium of swelling is reached in a relatively short period of time, ranging from 400 minutes for the system with 8 vol% of T3 to around 700 minutes for the system with 15 vol% of T3.

Figure 5: Swelling behaviour of hydrogels with two different concentrations of T3.

There is a noticeable effect of the hydrogel composition on the degree of swelling in such a way that a swelling ratio of 3.2 is reached for T3-8 hydrogels, whereas the swelling ratio for the T3-15 samples is only of 1.5. This is a consequence of the strong hydrophilic character of NVP. The rate of diffusion of PBS changes with the time of treatment, being maximal in the initial steps. The rate determining factor of the swelling process is the stress relaxation of the copolymer chains responding to the osmotic

swelling pressure. The decay of the rate of swelling is therefore enhanced for systems with high content of the hydrophilic component NVP.

Foetal cartilage cells seeded around hydrogel samples are used as preliminary assessment for determining the biocompatibility of this material. The cells were expected to proliferate towards the hydrogel. After 7 days, a Giemsa coloration fixed the living cells and Figure 6 shows the proliferation of the cells towards the samples which is opaque at the microscope. The cells surround the hydrogel and some can even be seen under the sample. Further tests are needed to confirm the complete colonization of the hydrogel by the cells.

Figure 6: Proliferation of foetal cartilage cells towards the hydrogel sample.

CONCLUSIONS

The synthesis of different monomers based on Tween 20 methacrylates was successfully achieved and the UV curing of the obtained material offered hydrogels of high interest for tissue engineering. The kinetics of polymerization was assessed by photorheology showing for example the increase of the viscosity with time and crosslinker concentration. Stress-strain curves of the hydrogels illustrated the influence of the water content on their mechanical performance, the elastic modulus ranging from 0.03 to 2.5 MPa. The swelling behaviour of the hydrogels was further investigated by gravimetry indicating that lower concentration of crosslinkers provides higher swelling ratio up to 3.2. Preliminary biocompatibility assays showed the viability of the cells in contact with the developed hydrogel. This intensive knowledge of neat hydrogels is currently leading to the development of reinforced hydrogel materials.

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